

Research Article

***Vincetoxicum schumannii*, a new name for *V. stenlobum*
(K.Schum.) Meve & Liede (Apocynaceae)**

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Abstract: A new name *Vincetoxicum schumannii* Deroliya, RameshKr. & Sanjeet Kumar is proposed here as a replacement name for *V. stenlobum* (K.Schum.) Meve & Liede, because the name is illegitimate, being a later homonym of *V. stenlobum* Shuttlew.

Keywords: *Astephanus*, nomenclature, Replacement name, Tanzania, *Tylophora*

Introduction

The genus *Vincetoxicum* Wolf, contains about 250 species is distributed throughout the tropics, subtropics of Africa, Asia, and Oceania, extending into temperate Eurasia (Endress *et al.*, 2018; POWO, 2025). In the current circumscription more than 30 genera of the *tribe* Asclepiadeae including genus *Tylophora* R.Br. are considered synonymous with *Vincetoxicum* Wolf (Ohwi, 1965; Liede, 1996; Liede *et al.*, 2002; Liede-Schumann *et al.*, 2012; 2016; Liede-Schumann and Meve, 2018; Endress *et al.*, 2018; Güven, 2019). Based on molecular phylogenetic studies, Liede-Schumann and Meve (2018) proposed 104 new combinations in *Vincetoxicum*, wherein *V. stenlobum* (K.Schum.) Meve & Liede, known from Kenya, Mozambique and Tanzania (Odorico *et al.* 2022, Hyde *et al.*, 2025), is a later homonym of *V. stenlobum* Shuttlew. (a synonym of *V. hirundinaria* Medik.), hence it is illegitimate according to Art. 53.1 of ICN (Turland *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, a replacement name is proposed herein.

Nomenclature

Vincetoxicum schumannii Deroliya, RameshKr. & Sanjeet Kumar, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Vincetoxicum stenolobum* (K.Schum.) Meve & Liede, *Phytotaxa* 369: 163. 2018, *nom. illeg.* non *V. stenolobum* Shuttlew., *Coup d'Oeil Fl. Toulon et d'Hyères* 16. 1891. *Astephanus stenolobus* K.Schum. in H.G.A.Engler (ed.), *Pflanzenw. Ost-Afrikas, C*: 321. 1895, non K.Schum. ex Engl. (1894), *nom. nud.* *Tylophora stenoloba* (K.Schum.) N.E.Br., *Bull. Misc. Inform. Kew* 1895(106): 257. 1895.

Lectotype (selected by Liede-Schumann and Meve (2018: 163): Tanzania, Tanga Dist., Doda, C.H.E.W. Holst 2977a (K, barcode: K000305327, image!).

Distribution: Kenya, Mozambique, and Tanzania.

Etymology: The specific epithet is chosen to honour Mr. K.M. Schumann, German (Silesian) Botanist for his remarkable contributions to the taxonomy of Tanzania.

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